

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the CAR ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the CAR ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the CAR ratio using a Mapping Research Topics using Library Research. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 636 journal publications regarding the CAR ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the CAR ratio are divided into 5 clusters and 217 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 58 topics around the influence of the CAR ratio and 31 topics about the determinants of the CAR ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around CAR ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

The use of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in banking has evolved over time. Initially, CAR was used as a tool to measure credit risk. However, along with the development of banking and the emergence of various new types of risk, CAR has developed into a comprehensive risk measuring tool. CAR is also used by central banks and regulators as a tool to monitor the financial health of banks around the world. In 1988, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) introduced the Basel Capital Accord, which became known as Basel I. Basel I set a minimum CAR requirement of 8% for credit risk. Basel I introduced a specific risk concept consisting of credit, market, and operational risks. CAR is calculated by dividing the capital owned by a bank by the specific risks faced by the bank. Basel I is the international standard for CAR measurements to this day. However, after the global financial crisis in 2008, the Basel Committee introduced Basel II which replaced Basel I. Basel II established more complex minimum CAR requirements, which included credit risk, market risk and operational risk. Basel II also encouraged banks to develop internal methods to measure their risks, which were later recognized by regulators (Hardiansyah et al., 2019).

Apart from Basel II, CAR has also developed in the form of Basel III. Basel III introduced stricter minimum CAR requirements and also added additional requirements such as leverage ratio and liquidity coverage ratio. Basel III also introduces a counter-cyclical concept, where CAR requirements can be increased during periods of economic growth to prevent a financial crisis. CAR is also used by investors and analysts to evaluate bank financial performance and compare one

bank with another. Investors and analysts can use the CAR ratio as a factor in deciding whether to invest in a bank or not. A high CAR shows that the bank is able to bear greater risks and is financially healthier. Overall, the use of CAR in banking has grown along with banking developments and new risks emerging. CAR has become an important tool for regulators, investors and analysts to assess banks' financial health and also monitor systemic risks. In order to maintain financial system stability, regulators continue to develop and update requirements (Anggoro, 2020).

Research on CAR in banking has become an increasingly popular topic and has attracted the attention of researchers. Several areas of research that have been carried out include the influence of CAR on bank financial performance, the influence of CAR on credit risk, the influence of CAR on market risk, and the influence of CAR on financial system stability. First, one study shows that there is a positive relationship between CAR and bank financial performance. The results of this research show that banks with higher CAR tend to have better financial performance (Joan et al., 2021). Second, other research shows that CAR has a significant effect on credit risk. The results of this research show that banks with higher CAR tend to have lower credit risk (Andri et al., 2021). Third, several studies have also revealed that CAR has an effect on financial system stability, indicating that higher CAR requirements can reduce the possibility of a financial crisis (Yuningsih, 2022). Fourth, other research shows that the use of the leverage ratio together with CAR can increase financial system stability. The results of this research show that the use of leverage ratios can reduce systemic risk and strengthen bank financial health (Rohman, 2022). Fifth, several studies have also revealed challenges in implementing CAR in banking, indicating that strict CAR implementation can reduce banks' ability to provide loans to customers, thereby affecting economic growth. Overall, research on CAR in banking continues to develop along with banking developments and new risks that emerge. The results of this research can help regulators, investors, and analysts in assessing the financial health of banks and also monitoring systemic risks (Dana, 2023).

The aim of this research is to map research topics around CAR in Islamic and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) Mapping Research Topics using Library Research to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding CAR. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research CAR. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the CAR ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is a financial ratio used to measure the level of capital adequacy or capital availability of a bank. CAR is the ratio between core capital and the bank's total risk assets. Core capital is the capital available to a bank to cover losses that may occur in bank operations, including paid-in capital and retained profits. Meanwhile, bank risk assets are the number of assets managed by the bank that can give rise to credit risk, market risk and operational risk. CAR is an important indicator in assessing a bank's financial health and its ability to survive during a financial crisis. Banks throughout the world are required to meet the minimum CAR requirements set by the banking supervisory authorities in their respective countries. The minimum CAR requirements that must be met can vary depending on the country and type of bank, but generally range between 8%-12%.

The higher a bank's CAR, the greater its ability to bear risk and the healthier its financial condition (Cindia et al., 2019).

Bibliometric studies are a quantitative research method carried out using bibliographic data, namely data regarding books, articles, journals and other scientific publications contained in a database or collection of references. The aim of a bibliometric study is to analyze patterns, trends and relationships between scientific publications in a particular field or discipline. Bibliometric studies can be carried out in various ways, such as conducting citation analysis, network analysis, and content analysis. Citation analysis involves counting the number and frequency of citations that a particular scientific publication receives from other scientific publications, while network analysis involves analyzing the relationships between scientific publications through citations, collaboration between authors, or other types of relationships. Content analysis involves analyzing the content of scientific publications, such as keywords, topics, or the language used. Bibliometric studies can provide useful insights for decision makers in a variety of fields, such as public policy, education, and research. In the academic field, bibliometric studies are often used to assess the quality or research productivity of an institution or individual, as well as to estimate trends and directions of development in certain scientific disciplines (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is software used to visualize bibliometric data and network analysis. This software was developed by Prof. Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman from Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands. VOSviewer has the ability to produce a network map that visualizes the relationship between the elements being analyzed, such as articles, authors, keywords or research subjects. Apart from that, VOSviewer can also carry out cluster analysis, which is analysis carried out to group elements that are similar or have similar relationship patterns into one group or cluster. The advantage of VOSviewer is the ability to visualize data in an interesting and easy to understand way, so that it can help researchers or decision makers in understanding the relationship patterns between elements in bibliometric data. Apart from that, VOSviewer also provides various advanced analysis features, such as analysis bibliometrics, cluster analysis, and factor analysis allow researchers to explore and understand bibliometric data in more depth. VOSviewer can also be integrated with various leading bibliometric databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar (van Eck NJ, 2022)

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research is a research method carried out with the aim of collecting, evaluating and synthesizing literature or scientific studies that are relevant to a particular research topic. This method is usually used at the initial stage of research to gain a better understanding of the topic to be researched, or at the final stage of research to conclude research results and identify gaps in the research conducted. A Mapping Research Topics using Library Research involves searching for literature sources or references that are relevant to the research topic. After that, the literature sources are analyzed and synthesized so that they can provide a clear and detailed picture of the research topic to be studied. Analysis is carried out by reading, understanding and evaluating related literature sources, including identifying the weaknesses and strengths of each literature source. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research have several advantages. First, this method allows researchers to gain a deep understanding of the topic to be researched, so that it can help in formulating better research questions and hypotheses. Second, this method can help researchers to identify existing research gaps and provide direction for future research. Third, Mapping Research Topics using Library Research can help researchers to expand their insight and knowledge in certain scientific disciplines. However, Mapping Research Topics using Library Research also have several weaknesses, such as limited literature sources that can

be found or accessed, the risk of selection bias and publication bias, and the difficulty of generalizing the results of Mapping Research Topics using Library Research due to variations in methodology and quality of the literature sources used (El- Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Mapping Research Topics using Library Research. The object of the research is the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category including the key words " Capital Adequacy Ratio " and "CAR" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding CAR using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around CAR using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around CAR using a Mapping Research Topics using Library Research (Rohimah et al., 2023a).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications around Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 636 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2008 to 2022. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about CAR by year

Year	Amount Publicatio n	Year	Amount Publicatio n
2008	1	2016	48
2009	2	2017	77
2010	2	2018	69
2011	3	2019	73
2012	7	2020	75
2013	15	2021	106

- Cluster 1, consists of 64 topic items, namely: ability, activity, addition, analytical method, annual financial statement, bank, bank profitability, banking, banking company, banking sector, bpr, business, capital, capital adequacy, case study, company, condition, country, credit, credit risk, criteria, data analysis, dependent variable, distribution, earnings, economy, efficiency, financial institution, financial performance, financial ratio, financial statement, form, fund, good corporate governance, health, hypothesis, idx, indicator, Indonesian stock exchange, investor, level, liquidity, negative effect, net interest margin, nim, operational efficiency, party, path analysis, performance, positive effect, problem, profit, profitability, public, quantitative approach, relationship, risk, role, sampling, significant positive effect, square, stock exchange, stock price, technique.
- Cluster 2, consists of 57 topic items, namely: data analysis, assets, independent banks, Indonesian people's banks, bank size, commercial banks, operating expenses, operating income, bei, Indonesian stock exchange, capital adequacy ratio, car, third party funds, panel data, deposit ratio, dpk, Indonesian effect, equity, explanatory research, hypothesis, Indonesian stock exchange, credit, ldr, loan deposit ratio, analysis method, non-performing loan, npl, car effect, dpk effect, loan effect, return effect, performance loan, Persero, banking company, population, profitability, purposive sampling, quantitative data, r square, ratio to return, return, roa, roe, sample, significant to return, spss, tbk, time series, f test, hypothesis test, t test.
- Cluster 3, consists of 55 topic items, namely: car influence analysis, analysis technique, annual report, application, autocorrelation test, bank Indonesia, classical assumption testing, coefficient, commercial bank, credit distribution, data analysis technique, data collection technique, determination test, documentation, effect, f test, financial report, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis testing, independent variable, influence, interest rate, lending, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis, normality test, positive influence, publication, purposive sampling technique, quantitative method, regression, research method, rest, sampling technique, secondary data, significance level value effect impact/influence, spss version, state, t test, test, third party fund, total sample, variable capital adequacy ratio.
- Cluster 4, consisting of 32 topic items: analysis method, independent sharia bank, sharia commercial bank, bi rate, data analysis method, fdr, financial services authority, financing, firm size, Indonesia, inflation, insignificant effect, Islamic banking, Islamic commercial banking, multiple linear regression, non-performing financing, npf, ojk, operational efficiency ratio, panel data regression, performing financing, population, purposive sampling, quantitative research, research data sample, sampling method, sharia commercial banking, significant negative effect, size, type.
- Cluster 5, consists of 9 topic items, namely: bopo, costs, evIEWS, expense, income, npl bopo, operating income, operational costs.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) on Islamic and Conventional Banking

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 57 effects of CAR on Islamic and Conventional Banking (Budianto, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohimah et al., 2023b) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023), namely:

(1) Fixed Assets to Capital/ATTM. CAR can influence ATTM because the higher the CAR, the greater the possibility that the bank has sufficient capital to finance long-term investments such as fixed assets. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have higher ATTM because they can finance more long-term investments.

(2) Share the profits from Mudharabah deposits. CAR can affect the profit sharing of mudharabah deposits because the higher the CAR, the smaller the bank's risk in doing so investment. This can increase customer confidence and enable banks to offer higher yields on deposits.

(3) Allowance for Impairment Losses. CAR can also affect reserves for impairment losses because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear losses due to decline in asset value. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have higher reserves for impairment losses and are better able to overcome credit risk.

(4) Core Capital and Supplementary Capital. CAR can influence the composition of bank capital because banks need to meet minimum requirements for Core Capital and Supplementary Capital. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to meet these requirements. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have sufficient and strong Core Capital and Supplementary Capital.

(5) Debt Financing. CAR can also affect a bank's ability to obtain financing through debt. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's possibility of obtaining debt financing with lower interest because the bank is considered safer and more credible by creditors.

(6) Profit sharing distribution. CAR can affect a bank's ability to distribute profits to shareholders and customers. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to distribute profits to shareholders and customers because the bank is considered more stable and able to overcome risks.

(7) Financial Sustainability Ratio/FSR. FSR measures a bank's ability to earn income and overcome risks. CAR can influence FSR because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to overcome risks and obtain stable income. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have better FSR.

(8) Financing Deposit Ratio/FDR. FDR measures the ratio of financing obtained from deposits to total bank financing. CAR can influence FDR because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to obtain financing from sources other than deposits. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have lower FDRs.

(9) Financial Distress. CAR can affect a bank's ability to overcome a bad financial situation. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to overcome crises and bad financial situations. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and less vulnerable to financial distress.

(10) Stock price. CAR can affect a bank's ability to invest because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to handle risks and obtain stable income. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have the ability to make larger and safer investments.

(11) Bank investment. CAR can affect a bank's ability to invest because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to handle risks and obtain stable income. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have the ability to make larger and safer investments.

(12) Initial Public Offering/IPO. CAR can influence a bank's ability to conduct an IPO because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to attract investor interest and provide stable profits in the future. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have the ability to conduct a better and more successful IPO.

(13) Number/volume of credit disbursed. CAR can influence the amount/volume of credit disbursed by banks because the higher the CAR, the

greater the bank's ability to handle risks and obtain stable income. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have the ability to distribute larger loans.

(14) Credit distribution policy. CAR can influence bank credit distribution policies because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to determine safe and responsible policies in distributing credit. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have more conservative and safe credit distribution policies.

(15) Credit granting decisions. CAR can influence bank credit granting decisions because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to evaluate risks and make wiser credit granting decisions. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have better and wiser lending decisions.

(16) Profitability. CAR can affect a bank's profit ability because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to handle risks and obtain stable income. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have better profit capabilities.

(17) Problematic credit/credit risk. CAR can influence a bank's credit risk level because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to handle risk and reduce the possibility of problem loans. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have a lower level of credit risk.

(18) Bad credit. CAR can influence the amount of bank bad credit because the higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to handle risks and reduce the possibility of bad credit occurring. Therefore, banks with high CAR tend to have a lower number of bad loans.

(19) Investment credit. The higher the CAR in banking, the greater the bank's ability to provide investment credit. This is because banks have greater capital and are able to withstand the risk of loss from the credit provided. On the other hand, if the CAR is low, banks will be more careful in providing investment credit because the risk of loss is higher. Therefore, a high CAR can increase investment credit in banks.

(20) Net profit. A high CAR can also have a positive impact on banking net profits. This is because banks that have sufficient capital can expand their business safely, thereby increasing revenue and net profit. Apart from that, a high CAR can also increase investor and customer confidence in banking, which can have a positive impact on business growth and net profit.

(21) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. LDR is a ratio that measures how much credit a bank provides compared to funds received from customers in the form of deposits. A high CAR can affect LDR in banking because banks have an obligation to maintain an adequate CAR level. If the CAR is low, banks will tend to limit lending, so that the LDR can be low. Conversely, if the CAR is high, the bank can provide more credit so that the LDR can increase.

(22) Loan Loss Provision/LLP. LLP is a reserve created by a bank to cover losses due to bad credit. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear the credit risk it takes. Thus, banks can create a larger amount of loss reserves, which will affect LLP positively.

(23) Profit management. Earnings management is an action taken by a company to influence financial reports to show better performance than it actually is. A high CAR can limit a bank's ability to carry out earnings management because banks must pay attention to applicable rules and regulations in managing their capital. This may reduce the bank's ability to shift revenues or delay recognition of expenses to improve financial statements.

(24) Murabahah Margin. Murabahah margin is the difference between the selling price and the buying price of an item in a buying and selling transaction carried out by a sharia bank. The higher the CAR, the lower the risk faced by the bank, so the bank can set a lower murabahah margin. This will increase the bank's competitiveness and enable the bank to offer more competitive prices to customers.

(25) Currency exchange rates. A high CAR shows that the bank has good financial strength, so it can strengthen investor confidence in its banks and a country's economy. This can strengthen the country's currency exchange rate, especially if the bank is considered a central bank or large bank that has an important role in the country's economy.

(26) The value of the company. A high CAR can increase investor confidence in a company, especially if the company is a bank. This can increase company value, because investors will feel more confident and comfortable in investing in companies that have good financial strength and are able to withstand risk.

(27) Net Interest Margin/NIM. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear risk, so the bank can offer lower interest rates to its customers. This can increase bank competitiveness and increase bank NIM.

(28) Non Performing Loans/NPL. A high CAR tends to reduce the bank's risk of NPLs. This is because banks have sufficient capital to cover the credit risks they take, so banks can carry out stricter credit assessments and minimize the risk of bad credit. Thus, the higher the CAR, the lower the bank's risk of NPLs.

(29) Non Performing Financing/NPF. The higher the CAR, the lower the bank's risk to NPF. Banks that have a high CAR tend to be more stringent in assessing credit risk, so they can minimize the risk to the NPF.

(30) Net Profit Margin/NPM. A high CAR can have a positive or negative impact on a bank's Net Profit Margin (NPM). In the short term, a high CAR can reduce NPM because banks need to finance larger capital. However, in the long term, a high CAR can increase NPM because banks tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers and increase income. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, thereby increasing the bank's NPM.

(31) Price changes. A high CAR tends to have a positive impact on bank share prices. This is because a high CAR shows investor confidence in the bank's ability to handle credit risk, thereby increasing investor confidence in bank performance and increasing demand for shares. On the other hand, a low CAR can reduce bank share prices because investors tend to worry about the credit risks taken by banks.

(32) Change in profit. A high CAR can have a positive impact on bank profits in the long term. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers and increase income. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, thereby increasing bank profits. However, in the short term, a high CAR can reduce bank profits because the bank needs to finance greater capital.

(33) Credit distribution. A high CAR can have a negative impact on bank credit distribution in the short term. This is because banks with high CAR tend to prefer to maintain their capital so that it does not decrease, so they do not prioritize credit distribution. However, in the long term, a high CAR can increase credit distribution because banks tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers and increase income. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, thereby increasing the bank's ability to provide credit.

(34) Interest income. A high CAR tends to have a positive impact on bank interest income. This is because a high CAR shows the bank's ability to handle the credit risks it takes, so that the bank can offer more competitive interest rates and attract new customers. Apart from that, banks with high CAR also tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so customers will prefer to place funds in banks that have high CAR.

(35) Income before tax. A high CAR can have a positive impact on a bank's pre-tax income in the long term. This is caused by banks with a high CAR tends to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so it can attract new customers and

increase income. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, thereby increasing the bank's ability to generate pre-tax income.

(36) Distribution of People's Business Credit/KUR. A high CAR can have a positive impact on the distribution of People's Business Credit (KUR) by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers and increase income. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, so that banks can provide credit at more competitive interest rates and attract customers who need KUR.

(37) Distribution of Home Ownership Credit/KPR. A high CAR can have a positive impact on the distribution of Home Ownership Credit (KPR) by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers who want to buy a house via KPR. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, so that banks can provide mortgages with more competitive interest rates and attract customers who need mortgages.

(38) Distribution of working capital credit. A high CAR can have a positive impact on working capital credit distribution by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers who need working capital credit. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, so that banks can provide working capital credit with more competitive interest rates and attract customers who need working capital credit.

(39) Mudharabah Financing. A high CAR can have a positive impact on Mudharabah financing by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers who need Mudharabah financing. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, so that banks can provide Mudharabah financing at more competitive interest rates and attract customers who need Mudharabah financing.

(40) Murabahah Financing. A high CAR can have a positive impact on Murabahah financing by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers who need Murabahah financing. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, so that banks can provide Murabahah financing with more competitive interest rates and attract customers who need Murabahah financing.

(41) Musyarakah Financing. A high CAR can have a positive impact on Musyarakah financing by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers who need Musyarakah financing. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, so that banks can provide Musyarakah financing with more competitive interest rates and attract customers who need Musyarakah financing.

(42) Disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. A high CAR can have a positive impact on CSR disclosure by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to have a good reputation and are appreciated by the public, so they have the desire to maintain a good image by carrying out activities that have a positive impact on society and the surrounding environment. In addition, a high CAR can also improve employee welfare, provide training, and encourage socially responsible practices.

(43) Percentage of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits. A high CAR can have a positive impact on the percentage of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits

by banks. This matter This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers who need Mudharabah deposit products. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, so that banks can provide more competitive profit sharing percentages and attract customers who need Mudharabah deposit products.

(44) Price Book Value/PBV. A high CAR can have a positive impact on a bank's PBV. This is because a bank's PBV is the ratio between the market value of the bank's shares and the book value of the bank, and a high CAR can indicate that the bank has sufficient financial strength to generate stable and reliable income in the future. In this case, investors tend to give a higher assessment to banks that have a high CAR and a higher PBV.

(45) Profitability. A high CAR can have a positive impact on bank profitability. This is because a high CAR can indicate that the bank has sufficient financial strength to generate stable and reliable income in the future. In addition, a high CAR can reduce credit risk costs and improve asset quality, thereby increasing overall bank profits.

(46) Bank risk. A high CAR can reduce bank risk. A fairly high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to bear the risks arising from its operational activities. In this case, banks tend to be able to reduce credit risk and market risk, thereby increasing stability and public trust in banks. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, thereby reducing the overall risk faced by banks.

(47) Liquidity risk. A high enough CAR can reduce liquidity risk. This is because a fairly high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient financial strength to cover its customers' payment obligations when they are due. In this case, banks tend to have sufficient resources to pay customers when they need money, thereby reducing liquidity risk and strengthening the bank's risk profile.

(48) Financing risk. A high enough CAR can reduce financing risk. This is because a fairly high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to bear the risks arising from the financing provided. In this case, banks tend to be able to reduce credit risk and other financing risks, such as financing risk in the form of securities and project financing risk. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, thereby reducing the overall risk faced by banks.

(49) Return On Assets/ROA. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on a bank's ROA. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient financial strength to generate stable and reliable income in the future. In this case, banks tend to have better trust from the public and can attract new customers who need financial products and services. Apart from that, a high CAR can also improve asset quality and reduce credit risk costs, thereby increasing the bank's overall ROA.

(50) Return On Equity/ROE. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on a bank's ROE. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to bear the risks arising from its operational activities, so that the bank tends to be able to generate stable and reliable profits in the future. In this case, banks tend to have better trust from the public and investors, so that they can increase the share value and overall ROE of the bank.

(51) Return On Deposit/ROD. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on a bank's ROD. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient financial strength to provide stable and profitable results relied on customer deposits. In this case, banks tend to be able to offer more competitive and attractive interest rates for customers to place their money on deposits, thereby increasing the bank's overall ROD.

(52) returns. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on bank stock returns. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to

bear the risks arising from its operational activities, so that the bank tends to be able to generate stable and reliable profits in the future. In this case, banks tend to have better trust from the public and investors, so that they can increase share value and overall bank share returns.

(53) Return deposit. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on bank deposit returns. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient financial strength to provide stable and reliable returns on customer deposits. In this case, banks tend to be able to offer more competitive and attractive interest rates for customers to place their money in deposits, thereby increasing overall bank deposit returns.

(54) Return for Mudharabah deposits. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on returns for Mudharabah Deposit Results. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to bear the risks arising from its operational activities, so that the bank can provide greater profits on Mudharabah deposits. In this case, banks tend to be able to offer better returns to customers who place funds in the form of Mudharabah deposits.

(55) Term deposit interest rates. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on Time Deposit Interest Rates. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient financial strength to provide stable and reliable returns on customer deposits. In this case, banks tend to be able to offer more competitive and attractive interest rates for customers to place their money in time deposits.

(56) Total financing. A high enough CAR can have a positive impact on Total Financing. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient financial strength to provide greater financing to customers. In this case, banks tend to be able to provide financing at more competitive interest rates, thereby increasing the bank's overall total financing.

(57) MSMEs. A fairly high CAR can have a positive impact on financing for MSMEs. This is because a high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to bear the risks arising from its operational activities, so that the bank can provide greater financing to MSMEs. In this case, banks tend to be able to provide financing at lower interest rates, so that they can help improve the performance and growth of MSMEs and support overall economic growth.

(58) Disclosure of Islamic Social Reporting/ISR. A high CAR can have a positive impact on ISR disclosure by banks. This is because banks with high CAR tend to be more stable and trustworthy for customers, so they can attract new customers who care about banking practices that are in line with Islamic values. Apart from that, a high CAR can also increase a bank's reputation and public trust, so that banks tend to be more committed to disclosing transparent financial and social reports.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Determinant Variables of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 31 CAR determinant variables in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. Operational Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) is an indicator of banking operational performance which measures the level of efficiency of operational costs to operational income. The lower the BOPO, the better the banking operational performance, and this can have a positive impact on CAR. In this case, banks can obtain higher profitability with lower operational costs, thereby increasing CAR.

(2) Contingencies. Contingencies refer to possible losses that may arise in the future, such as bad credit, investment losses, and other risks. The greater the number of contingencies a bank has, the greater the risk the bank must bear and

the greater the capital requirements needed to meet CAR requirements. Therefore, if the number of contingencies is higher, the bank's CAR will tend to decrease.

(3) Current Ratio. Current Ratio is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to pay its short-term obligations with current assets. The higher the Current Ratio, the greater the bank's ability to pay its obligations in the short term, so that the bank can reduce liquidity risk and increase CAR. In this case, banks tend to have sufficient capital to bear the risks of their operational activities.

(4) Derivatives. Derivatives are financial instruments used by banks to protect themselves from market risks, such as interest risk and currency risk. The use of derivatives can increase potential profits, but can also increase potential losses, so it can have an impact on CAR. The greater the risk borne by the bank in using derivatives, the greater the capital requirements needed to meet CAR requirements. Therefore, banks need to calculate the risks and benefits of using derivatives wisely to ensure the availability of sufficient capital to meet CAR requirements. Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. The higher the DER, the greater the company's financial risk. In this case, the higher the DER, the lower the CAR, because debt can burden the company's capital and reduce the level of capital adequacy that the company can use. Conversely, the lower the DER, the higher the CAR, because the company has more capital to support risks and business activities.

(5) Efficiency. Efficiency in this case refers to the bank's ability to manage available resources effectively and efficiently. The more efficient a bank is in managing resources, the greater its ability to build capital and maintain sufficient CAR. Therefore, the higher the efficiency, the higher the CAR.

(6) Micro fundamental factors. Micro fundamental factors such as economic conditions, regulations, industry competition and management quality can in

(7) influence CAR. The better the economic conditions, the stronger the regulations and management, and the less competition in the industry, the higher the CAR. Conversely, the worse the economic conditions, the weaker the regulations and management, and the tighter the competition in the industry, the lower the CAR.

(8) Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR. The higher the FDR, the higher the bank's risk due to high dependence on unstable funding sources. In this case, the higher the FDR, the lower the CAR, because financing can burden the company's capital and reduce the level of capital adequacy that the company can use. Conversely, the lower the FDR, the higher the CAR, because the bank has more capital to support risks and business activities.

(9) Statutory Reserve Requirement. Minimum statutory reserves are the amount of money that banks must maintain in current accounts at the central bank as a form of liquidity. The effect of minimum statutory reserves on CAR in banking is relatively small because minimum statutory reserves only affect bank liquidity and are not directly related to capital.

(10) Good Corporate Governance/GCG. GCG is good and correct corporate governance which includes the responsibilities of the board of directors, management and stakeholders. Good GCG can influence banking CAR by increasing investor confidence and improving overall company performance.

(11) The amount of money in circulation. The money supply refers to the amount of money that is in the hands of the public and can be used to carry out transactions. The effect of money supply on CAR in banking depends on overall economic conditions. If the money supply increases, credit demand will increase, which in turn can increase credit risk and affect CAR.

(12) Commitment. Commitment in a banking context refers to a bank's commitment to fulfill their financial obligations to third parties. The effect of commitment on CAR on banks depends on the bank's level of commitment. If a bank has a high level of commitment in fulfilling its financial obligations, it is likely that the bank will have a lower level of risk and a higher CAR.

(13) Asset quality. Asset quality reflects how good a bank's credit portfolio is and the bank's ability to earn income from that portfolio. Poor asset quality can reduce the total value of bank assets and increase credit risk. This can have an impact on CAR in banking because CAR is calculated by dividing bank capital by the total risk taken. If credit risk increases due to poor asset quality, CAR will decrease.

(14) Management quality. Management quality reflects the ability of bank management to manage risk and generate income. Good management can influence CAR in banking by reducing risk and increasing profits. Poor management quality can increase risks and reduce profits, thereby affecting CAR.

(15) Bad credit. Bad credit can reduce asset quality and increase bank credit risk. This can have an impact on CAR in banking because CAR is calculated by dividing bank capital by the total risk taken. If credit risk increases due to bad credit, the CAR will decrease.

(16) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. A high LDR may indicate that the bank relies on loans to finance their operations, which may increase risk. A low LDR can indicate that the bank has better liquidity and can reduce risk. The effect of LDR on CAR in banking depends on the level of risk associated with the loans and deposits. If loans have greater risk than deposits, then a high LDR can reduce CAR.

(17) Merger. The effect of a merger on CAR depends on several factors, such as the size of the merged bank, level of efficiency, and good risk management. If the merger is done correctly, the merged bank can experience an increase in CAR due to combining resources and reducing costs. However, if the merger is not properly regulated, bank risk can increase and cause a decrease in CAR.

(18) Net Interest Margin/NIM. The greater the NIM, the greater the bank's interest income, which can increase CAR because the bank has more capital. However, if the NIM is too high, the bank may be inclined to take on higher risks in an attempt to increase earnings, which can reduce the CAR.

(19) Net Profit Margin/NPM. An increase in NPM can indicate better operational efficiency and better risk management, which can help increase CAR. However, if the NPM is too high, the bank may take on higher risks in an attempt to increase profits, which can reduce the CAR.

(20) Non Performing Financing/NPF. If the NPF level is high, the bank may experience significant losses, which may lead to a decrease in CAR. Therefore, banks must ensure that appropriate credit risk management is implemented to reduce NPF risk and keep CAR stable.

(21) Non Performing Loans/NPL. If the bank's NPL increases, the bank will lose assets that should earn interest, which in the end it does impact on bank profits. This can reduce CAR because banks have to prepare reserves to cover losses resulting from NPL.

(22) Covid-19 pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has had a major impact on the economy and business, including banking. In this pandemic, there has been a decrease in income and an increase in credit risk, which in the end can affect banks' CAR. In the Covid-19 pandemic situation, banks may need to increase their capital to meet CAR requirements, because credit risk increases.

(23) Net Open Position. Net foreign exchange position can affect a bank's CAR, because CAR is calculated based on core capital compared to risk assets. A strong net foreign exchange position can help banks to strengthen their core capital and ultimately improve CAR.

(24) Profitability. Good bank profitability can increase CAR, because banks can generate greater profits from their assets. The resulting profits can be used to strengthen core capital, which in turn can increase CAR. However, poor profitability can lower the CAR because the bank may need to use its core capital to cover losses and other weaknesses.

(25) Liquidity risk. Liquidity risk can have a negative impact on CAR, because if a bank faces liquidity difficulties, the bank will be forced to use its capital to fulfill payment obligations that must be made immediately. This can reduce the amount of capital available and reduce the bank's CAR.

(26) Credit risk. Credit risk can also affect CAR. If a bank experiences an increase in non-performing loans or NPLs, the bank will be forced to reduce its capital to cover these losses. This will reduce the amount of capital available and lower the CAR.

(27) Return On Assets/ROA. If ROA increases, this can increase bank profits, which can be used to strengthen bank capital and increase CAR.

(28) Return On Equity/ROE. If ROE increases, this can increase bank profits, which can be used to strengthen bank capital and increase CAR. However, keep in mind that increasing ROE does not always mean increasing CAR, depending on how the profit is used by the bank.

(29) Return On Capital Employed/ROCE. The higher the ROCE, the more effective the bank is in generating profits from the use of its capital. A high ROCE can indicate that a bank can earn sufficient profits to meet its capital needs and maintain or increase its CAR.

(30) Risk. All types of risks, such as credit risk, liquidity risk and market risk, can affect a bank's CAR. Risk that is too high can cause the bank to experience losses and reduce the capital it has, thus affecting the CAR. Therefore, good and effective risk management is very important to maintain a healthy CAR.

(31) Bank size. Bank size can also affect CAR. Larger banks tend to have more resources and capital available, and thus can maintain higher CAR. However, larger banks also tend to have risks that are more complex and more difficult to manage, so they need better and more effective risk management to maintain a healthy CAR.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 2008 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 636 articles publication journal. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the CAR ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking are divided into 5 clusters and 217 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 64 topics, cluster 2 consists of 57 topics, clusters 3 consists of 55 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 32 topics. Third, based on mapping Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 58 topics related to the influence of the CAR ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: Fixed Assets to Capital/ATM, Mudharabah deposit profit sharing, Allowance for Impairment Losses, Core Capital and Supplementary Capital, Debt Financing, Profit sharing distribution, Financial Sustainability Ratio/FSR, Financing Deposit Ratio/FDR, Financial Distress, stock prices, bank investment, Initial Public Offering/IPO, total volume of credit disbursed, credit distribution policy, decisions credit provision, profitability, problem credit/credit risk, bad credit, investment credit, net profit, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Loan Loss Provision/LLP, profit management, Murabahah margin, currency exchange rate, company value, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Non Performing Loan/NPL, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Net Profit Margin/NPM, changes prices, changes in profit, credit distribution, interest income, income before tax, distribution of People's Business Credit/KUR, distribution of Home Ownership Credit/KPR, distribution of working capital credit, Mudharabah financing, Murabahah, Musyarakah, Disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR, Percentage of shares Mudharabah deposit results, Price Book Value/PBV, profitability, bank risk, liquidity risk, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return On

Deposit/ROD, stock returns, deposit returns, Mudharabah deposit profit sharing returns, interest rates term deposits, total financing, MSMEs, and disclosure of Islamic Social Reporting/ISR.

And there are 31 topics related to the determinants of the CAR ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO, Contingencies, Current Ratio, Derivatives, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, efficiency, micro fundamental factors, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, minimum statutory reserves, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, money supply, commitment, asset quality, quality management, bad credit, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, merger, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Net Profit Margin/NPM, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Non Performing Loan/NPL, pandemic covid-19, net foreign exchange position, profitability, liquidity risk, credit risk, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return On Capital Employed/ROCE, risk, and bank size.

Suggestion

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that it can The following research results were obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the Mapping Research Topics using Library Research can be explained in a more complex way.

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